

- a, R₁=R₂=H
 b; R₁=H, R₂=Cl
 c; R₁=Cl, R₂=H
 d; R₁=H, R₂=CH₃

Chart 1

**Photochemical Singlet Oxygenation of
 4,5-Diaryl-2-(benzylthio)imidazoles.
 Formation of *N,N'*-Diaryl-*S*-
 benzylisothioureas**

JESSYMOL MATHEW and E. PURUSHOTHAMAN*

School of Chemical Sciences, Mahatma Gandhi University,
 Kottayam-686 631

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IN view of our interest in the selective photochemical reactions of bichromophoric heterocyclic systems containing a stilbene chromophore, we carried out a systematic investigation on the photochemistry of 4,5-diarylimidazole-2-thiones (1). Contrary to our expectation that a regioselective photochemical 1,2-addition of singlet oxygen at the imidazole ring systems to the corresponding diarylthioureas as in 2 would occur on dye-sensitised irradiation, the imidazole-2-thione gave a decomposed resinous material which could not be isolated and identified. Unsensitised photooxidation of the imidazole-2-thione chromophore in 1 underwent a facile conversion to the corresponding bis(imidazol-2-yl)sulphide (3)¹ (Chart 1). This observation prompted us to explore the possibility of photochemical singlet oxygenation of the imidazole-2-thiols by protecting the thiol function. In this paper, we describe the synthesis of 4,5-diaryl-2-(benzylthio)imidazoles (4)

starting from the corresponding 4,5-diarylimidazole-2-thiones (1) and their photochemical singlet oxygenation to yield the *N,N'*-diaryl-*S*-benzylisothioureas (5) on a preparative scale.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded in open capillaries in a hot-stage melting point apparatus. Irradiations were carried out in a water-cooled immersion type photochemical reactor with quartz thimbles using a high-pressure 125 W mercury-quartz lamp. Uv spectra were recorded in aldehyde-free ethanol, ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrometer and pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a JEOL FX-900 spectrometer. Precoated silica gel plates were used for analytical tlc. All solvents used were distilled and dried.

4,5-Diarylimidazole-2-thiol (1): The synthesis was carried out by the improved method¹. In a typical procedure, a mixture of acyloin (10 mmol) and ammonium thiocyanate (10 mmol) in isoamyl alcohol (10 ml) was refluxed for 1–5 h. The product was found to crystallise on cooling the reaction mixture or keeping it overnight or on removal of the solvent. The unreacted acyloin was removed by washing with ether and the ammonium thiocyanate by washing with water. The product was crystallised to afford white or light yellow crystals.

4,5-Diaryl-2-(benzylthio)imidazoles (4a–d): A mixture of 4,5-diarylimidazole-2-thiol (10 mmol) in alcohol (20 ml) and sodium hydroxide (0.2 g, 5 mmol) in water (10 ml) was heated on a water-bath until the thiol dissolved. Then benzyl chloride (1.2 g, 10 mmol) was added to it slowly with stirring. The resulting solid was washed with ether to remove the excess benzyl chloride, dried and recrystallised from toluene to afford white crystals.

* Present address. Department of Chemistry, Calicut University, Kerala-673 635.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 4a–d*

Compd. no.	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Spectral data
4a	73	183	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ S	$\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ) 282 (4.26), 222 nm (4.38); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 100 cm ⁻¹ (NH); δ 6.6 (16H, m, ArH), 3.76 (2H, s, CH ₂)
4b	96	187	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ SCl ₂	$\lambda_{\max}$ 278 (4.23), 235 nm (4.55); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 100 cm ⁻¹ (NH); δ 6.8–6.4 (14H, m, ArH), 3.8 (2H, s, CH ₂)
4c	95	199	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₂ SCl ₂	$\lambda_{\max}$ 274 (4.18), 242 nm (4.62); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 080 cm ⁻¹ (NH); δ 6.64–6.4 (14H, m, ArH), 3.84 (2H, s, CH ₂)
4d	68	174	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ S	$\lambda_{\max}$ 284 (4.21), 239 nm (4.56); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 060 cm ⁻¹ (NH); δ 7.2 (14H, m, ArH), 4.1 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.3 (6H, s, CH ₃)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

TABLE 2—SINGLET OXYGENATION OF COMPOUNDS 4a–d AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 5a–d*

Compd. irradiated	Time of irradiation (h)	Product	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	Spectral data
4a	7	5a	62	153	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	$\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ) 301 (4.30), 276 nm (4.48); $\nu_{\max}$ 3080 (NH), 1 710, 1 630 cm ⁻¹ (C=O); δ 7.56–7.20 (5H, m, ArH), 6.84–6.52 (10H, m, ArH), 4.12 (2H, s, CH ₂)
4b	3	5b	51	194	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ Cl ₂ O ₂ S	$\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ) 318 (4.44), 2.88 nm (4.55); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 100 (NH), 1 710, 1 630 cm ⁻¹ (C=O); δ 7.52–7.08 (8H, m, ArH), 4.08 (2H, s, CH ₂)
4c	13	5c	35	151	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ Cl ₂ O ₂ S	$\nu_{\max}$ 3 080 (NH), 1 710, 1 630 cm ⁻¹ (C=O)
4d	8	5d	38	152	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	$\lambda_{\max}$ (log ϵ) 318 (4.40), 291 nm (4.50); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 080 (NH), 1 700, 1 630 cm ⁻¹ (C=O); δ 8.04 (5H, m, ArH), 7.34 (8H, m, ArH), 4.50 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.42 (6H, m, CH ₃)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

Singlet oxygenation of 4,5-diaryl-2-(benzylthio)imidazole. Formation of N,N'-diaroyl-S-benzylisothioureas (5a–d): A solution containing 4,5-diaryl-2-(benzylthio)imidazole (3 mmol) and methylene blue (≈ 15 mg) in ethanol (300 ml) was irradiated in a photochemical reactor under a slow stream of oxygen for 3–13 h for different compounds. The completion of the reaction was monitored by tlc. The product deposited on the sides of the reaction vessel was separated, washed with ethanol, dried and recrystallised from benzene to yield white crystals.

Results and Discussion

As stated in the experimental section, the 4,5-diaryl-2-(benzylthio)imidazoles (4a–d) were prepared by the reaction of different substituted imidazole-2-thiols with benzyl chloride in aqueous alkali. Their spectral data are presented in Table 1. Irradiation of dilute solution of 4a–d (0.05 M) in ethanol containing methylene blue in a stream of air produced the N,N'-dibenzoyl-S-benzylisothioureas (5a–d). The latter were identified by analysis and spectral data. The compounds 5 furnished on basic hydrolysis followed by acidification, benzoic acid, which confirmed the presence of benzoyl grouping. The details of compounds 5 are given in Table 2.

The formation of the compounds 5 can be explained mechanistically by the type-II Gollnick process². In this process, the photochemically

generated singlet oxygen reacts with the enamine bond in the heterodiene system present in imidazole-2-thiols through a 1,2-addition in a concerted manner to give the dioxetanes which are usually unstable and undergo fragmentation to two carbonyl compounds. The tentative mechanistic pathway can be represented as in Scheme 1 by analogy with the mechanism of singlet oxygenation of imidazoles substituted both at 2- and 5-positions³. Since the

Scheme 1

products are formed without the addition of bases, the possibility of formation of hydroperoxy intermediate, as envisaged⁴ in 2,4,5-triphenylimidazoles, cannot be suggested.

In conclusion, we have shown that the derivatization of thiol as benzylthio group actually prevents

the photosensitive nature of the thiol function in imidazole-2-thiols and the photochemical singlet oxygenation of 4,5-diaryl-2-(benzylthio)imidazoles proceeds in a preparative scale to the *N,N'*-diaroyl-*S*-benzylisothiureas. The ease at which the photochemical singlet oxygenation takes place in alcoholic solvents points to the synthetic potential of this reaction.

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